

The Impact and Control of Climate Change in European Coastal Cities: A brief summary of SCORE Project

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ABSTRACT

Extreme weather events, coastal erosion, and sea-level rise will be the main environmental disaster causes of deaths in the world if no actions are taken to increase the climate resilience of coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advances in knowledge and resilience require progress in data acquisition and smart technologies. There is already an Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) integrated with smart technologies, which has the potential to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities. However, this approach has not yet been adequately understood and coordinated at the European level. The “Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities (acronym SCORE)” project, which aims to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities and is financed by HORIZON 2020, has been accepted by the European Union Commission. SCORE aims to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities and settlements through co-designed, codeveloped, deployed, tested, and demonstrated innovative EBA, smart technologies, and hybrid Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). SCORE is based on Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL), a new concept that expands the Living Labs to a wider vision for coastal cities and settlements. This study includes a descriptive and honest explanation of the promotion of the SCORE project, which was accepted by the European Commission and financed by HORIZON 2020, and the work to be done.

Keywords: Climate resilience, climate change, EBA, NBS, living labs

INTRODUCTION

Global projections on the concept of climate change mainly indicate global warming, sea-level rise, and increases in climatic extremes (Allen and Ingram, 2002; IPCC, 2007; Allan and Soden, 2008). The main drivers of coastal morphology evolution related to climate change are wave characteristics, storm frequency/intensity, and river floods. Delta plains are densely populated, and large numbers of people are often impacted as a result of external terrestrial influences (e.g., river floods) and/or external marine influences (storm surges, erosion). Estuaries and deltas, some of the largest sedimentary deposits in the world, are widely recognized as highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, particularly sea-level rise and changes in runoff, as well as being subject to stresses imposed by human modification of catchment and delta plain land use.

The intensification of extreme coastal events, coastal erosion, and sea-level rise under climate change could make living near the coast high-risk. A research study by the European Commission's Joint Research Center projected those deaths caused by extreme weather in Europe could rise from 3,000 a year between 1981 and 2010 to 152,000 between 2071 and 2100 if no actions are taken to mitigate climate change impacts and improve policies to increase the resilience of European coastal cities (Forzieri et al., 2017). The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancement in knowledge requires progress in data acquisition and forecasting with the level of detail and timing useful for real-scenario interventions (Rizvi and van Riel, 2018). An Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) integrated with smart technologies (e.g., smart sensing and digital twin solutions) has the potential to increase the climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, this approach is not yet

adequately understood and coordinated at the European level and therefore does not reach its full potential (Neumann et al., 2015). SCORE aims to reduce the impacts of sea-level rise and extreme events due to climate change on European coastal cities and settlements utilizing co-designed, co-developed, deployed, tested, and demonstrated innovative EBAs, smart technologies, and hybrid Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs), while facilitating financial sustainability. SCORE provides scientific evidence for the application of EBAs, and best practices for their design, replication, and scalability in the context of smart coastal cities.

The overarching objective of SCORE is to study, design, develop, monitor, and validate robust adaptation measures in coastal and low-lying areas to protect them from increasing climate and sea level risks, including coastal flooding and erosion, thus enhancing their overall long-term resilience. SCORE is constructed around specific objectives (SOs) addressing gaps in terms of knowledge, innovation, social acceptance, market opportunity, financing, and policy. The project will involve citizen science in providing prototype coastal city early-warning systems and will enable smart, instant monitoring and control of climate resilience in European coastal cities through open, accessible spatial 'digital twin' tools. Along with the Samsun city of Turkey, the project seeks to advance the control of climate resilience in 10 CCLLs in Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Koper, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland.

METHOD

The overarching concept of SCORE (Figure 1) is to develop a framework for the development, deployment, evaluation, and uptake of integrated Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBA) and smart technologies as the optimum route to improving the climate resilience of European coastal cities in a rapid, equitable and sustainable way. This will be achieved through the establishment of a Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL) infrastructure involving multiple stakeholders and supported by novel digital technologies for 1. Projections of climate change and coastal erosion at local and regional levels in the CCLLs with and without different mitigation interventions; 2. Monitoring coastal climate change and developing early-warning systems at a local level via a network of low-cost smart sensors deployed through citizen science activities with local coastal communities; 3. Collecting and sharing evidence of EBA effectiveness through a high-quality SCORE ICT Platform (SIP); 4. Increasing the financial resilience of coastal cities through financial risk assessment tools; 5. Supporting decision-making in the governance of coastal cities through the development of digital twin prototypes to analyze optimal corrective actions for sustainable, equitable, and cost-effective climate resilience.

Figure 1. Overview of SCORE concept

SCORE is an ambitious project that focuses on increasing climate resilience in European coastal cities and settlements using an innovative integrated approach of EBAs, CCLs, sensing technologies, and twin digital solutions. It adopts the CCLL concept that embraces participatory processes, co-design, co-development, and implementation. Demonstrating the efficacy of EBAs is central in the project and at the same time ensuring that all elements of complex management are taken into account. Specifically, WPs have been carefully designed to work together to guarantee stakeholder engagement within increasing shells of decision levels from the local inhabitants up to the international policy level. Another aspect is the establishment of European leadership which goes together with the creation of market opportunities of SCORE's approach in Europe and globally. SCORE's innovative approach also includes a refined exploitation strategy and specific capacity-building activities to expand and apply its findings to other EU countries and beyond (including developing countries).

SCORE has 10 CCLs in 9 different European countries and Turkey (Figure 2). Hazards and their sectoral impacts in these 10 CCLs were visualized separately as shown in Figure 2 and summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2. CCLL visualization

The 10 WPs follow a carefully designed structure according to four logical phases composed of foundation (WP1, WP2, WP3), building evidence (WP4, WP5), consolidation (WP6, WP7, WP8), and Synergy and exploitation actions (WP9), all managed via WP10 (Figure 3).

Table 1. Actual hazard and sectoral impacts of each CCLLs

CCLLs	Hazards	Sectoral Impacts
Barcelona, Spain 	Coastal Flooding Land Flooding Coastal Erosion Coastal Storm Surge	Risk to tourism Loss of Cultural Heritage Damage to Commercial Buildings Damage to Residential Buildings Energy Networks Loss of animal habitat Damage to civil infrastructure

<p>Benidorm, Spain</p>	<p>Coastal Flooding Coastal Erosion Coastal Surge Storm</p>	<p>Risk to tourism Loss of Cultural Heritage Damage to Residential Buildings Risk to local economy</p>
<p>Dublin, Ireland</p>	<p>Coastal Erosion Coastal Surge Storm</p>	<p>Risk to tourism Loss of Cultural Heritage Damage to Commercial Buildings Damage to Residential Buildings Energy Networks Damage to civil infrastructure</p>
<p>Gdansk, Poland</p>	<p>Coastal Flooding Land Flooding</p>	<p>Risk to tourism Loss of Cultural Heritage Damage to Commercial Buildings Damage to Residential Buildings Energy Networks Damage to civil infrastructure</p>
<p>Koper, Slovenia</p>	<p>Coastal Flooding Coastal Surge Storm</p>	<p>Risk to tourism Loss of Cultural Heritage Damage to Residential Buildings Damage to civil infrastructure</p>

Figure 3. SCORE WPs structure

Firstly, WP1 will map the baseline exposure and risk of extreme climate impacts on coastal cities, WP2 will Design, Implementation, and Evaluate Coastal City Living Labs, then WP3 will produce regional and local projections for the CCLL in addition to the analyses, modelling, and uncertainties for the results. CCLL co-warning and co-monitoring will be produced in WP4 and the WP5 will work on the pre/post-EBA interventions evidence collection and knowledge marketplace. The strategies to increase the financial resilience of coastal cities will be produced in WP6 and the socio-economic assessment of adaptation strategies and policy recommendations will be done in WP7. WP8 is responsible for the development of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin solution prototypes, while WP9 will integrate the results of all the WPs for the dissemination, communication, and exploitation process. Finally, SCORE will be coordinated and managed to ensure that the project meets its milestones on time and within a budget (WP10).

CONCLUSION

SCORE will develop and deliver a new generation of tools and methodologies, as well as validated EBAs, to enhance climate resilience in European coastal cities and settlements through the adaptation to sea-level rise and extreme events risks. Through CCLLs and smart technologies, the project will not only prove the technical feasibility of EBAs in real-life settings but also demonstrate the socio-economic viability of EBA prototypes. CCLLs will enable showcasing and validation of the solutions towards the creation of a global market for the integration of EBAs and smart technologies. Several of the EBAs that will be demonstrated have already been proven in terms of efficacy, but their large-scale, systematic use is far from being achieved, and their integration with the concept of smart cities is yet to be tested and proven. Several of them have reached TRLs around 4-5; however, they need to be advanced to higher TRLs (7-8) through a concerted action aimed at proving their efficacy in real life, as in this project by integrating EBAs with the digital twin system to monitor the climate resilience of the coastal cities. This will strongly enhance confidence in EBAs, both from an end-user and a business perspective, thus accelerating their systematic adoption. SCORE will generate a robust, EU-wide evidence base and develop a European reference framework for climate resilience adaptations in coastal cities.

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